

Studies on Thioindigoid Dyes

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Preparation and properties of three classes of dyes obtained by the condensation of 4-bromo-3-hydroxythionaphthene with acenaphthenequinones, phenanthraquinones and benzaldehydes have been reported. The λ_{\max} values have been noted and reasons for the variation of colour in the dyes have been offered.

IN this communication we report the preparation and properties of the dyes shown in structures I a-d, II a-c and III a-c which have been obtained by the condensation of 4-bromo-3-hydroxythionaphthene¹ with the appropriate acenaphthenequinones, phenanthraquinones and benzaldehydes.

	R	R'	R''
Ia	H	H	H
Ib	OCH ₃	H	H
Ic	H	Cl	H
Id	H	NO ₂	NO ₂

The acenaphthylene indigos (I a-d) possess intense violet-brown, chocolate-brown or brownish red colour. The dyes offered great resistance to reduction by hydrosulphite and formed the greenish yellow vats. The shades on cotton could not be fully developed. Details about the dyes are given in Table.

A comparison of the λ_{\max} values of the dyes Ia and Ib with similar dyes having the bromine atom ^{a-a} in positions 5-, 6-, and 7-, respectively, reveals that on this basis the depth of colour of the dyes could be arranged as under: 5-bromo dye > 4-bromo dye > 7-bromo dye.

It will, however, be noticed from the absorption data (Table) that while a methoxy substituent at position 1' (of the acenaphthene moiety) has a bathochromic effect, a chlorine atom at 3' or two or nitro groups at 3' and 4', cause the opposite effect. The reasons for these apparently anomalous results are not obvious from the usual electronic considerations and the explanations are without doubt more involved.

	R
IIa	H
IIb	N(CH ₃) ₂
IIc	NO ₂

TABLE I

Dye	Name of Reactants	Name of dye	Appearance Yield %	Solvent of crystallisation M.P.C.	λ_{\max} in m μ
Ia	T + AQ	2-(4-Bromo)-thionaphthene-AI	Violet brown 78	Pyridine 269-270	527
Ib	T + Methoxy-AQ	2-(4-Bromo)-thionaphthene-8'-(1-methoxy) AI	Violet brown 78	Pyridine 292-293	520
Ic	T + 3-Chloro-AQ	2-(4-Bromo)-thionaphthene-8'-(3-chloro)-AI	Brownish red 72	Pyridine 337-338	515
Id	T + 3 : 4-Dinitro-AQ	2-(4-Bromo)-thionaphthene-8'-(2'-4'-dinitro)-AI	Chocolate 74	Pyridine 299-300	510
IIa	T + Benzaldehyde	B-2-(4-Bromo) 3-oxy 2,3 dihydro thionaphthene	Intense Yellow 82	Ethanol 137-138	440
IIb	T + N,N-Dimethylamino-benzaldehyde	4'-Dimethylamino-B-2-(4-Bromo) 3-oxy 2,3 dihydrothionaphthene	Violet 84	Acetic acid 195-196	490
IIc	T + 4-Nitrobenzaldehyde	4'-Nitro-B-2-(4-Bromo) 3-oxy 2,3 dihydro thionaphthene	Orange 80	Acetic acid 207-208	442
IIIa	T + PQ	2-(4-Bromo)-thionaphthene-9'-PI	Black 68	Pyridine 300-302	554
IIIb	T + 2-Nitro-PQ	2-(4-Bromo)-thionaphthene-9'-(2'-nitro)-PI	Deep chocolate 72	Pyridine 325(d)	540
IIIc	T + 2:7-Dinitro-PQ	2-(4-Bromo)-thionaphthene-9'-(2'-7'-dinitro)-PI	Brownish black 78	Pyridine 360	545

T=4-Bromo-3-hydroxythionaphthene, AQ=Acenaphthene quinone, AI=Acenaphthyleneindigo, B=benzylidene, PQ=Phenanthraquinone, PI=Phenanthrene indigo.

The shades of the benzylidene dyes IIa-c reported herein vary from violet to orange to intense yellow. They are all soluble in methanol, ethanol, acetic acid, xylene, pyridine etc., δ Attempts to reduce these dyes by hydrosulphite were not quite successful and even moderate shades could not be developed on cotton. The λ_{\max} values of the dyes (*vide* Table) when compared with similar dyes with the position of the bromine atom in thionaphthene substrate varying ²⁻⁴ from 5 to 6 to 7, now enable us to conclude that the depth of colour varies in these series also as follows :

5-bromo dye > 4-bromo dye > 7-bromo dye > 6-bromo dye.

	R	R'
IIIa	H	H
IIIb	NO ₂	H
IIIc	NO ₂	NO ₂

The phenanthrene indigos IIIa-c all have intense colour (black, deep-chocolate, and brown-black) but these dyes again could not be uniformly developed on cotton from the hydrosulphite vats. These dyes, however, absorb maximally at appreciably higher wavelength than those discussed in the previous paragraphs, apparently because the three aromatic π sextets of the phenanthrene system extend the area of the electron cloud and thus lead to enhanced absorption maxima. A nitro group at position 2 causes a hypsochromic effect, compared to the unsubstituted dye, due obviously to electron withdrawal from the phenanthrene ring system. The two nitro groups at 2 and 7, however, cause a slightly lesser hypsochromic effect, than a single nitro group at 2 probably because these two nitro groups somewhat neutralise one another's effect on the main chromophore system. However, when the λ_{\max} values of the dyes obtained by condensation of 4-

bromo-, 5-bromo-, 6-bromo-, and 7-bromo-3-hydroxythionaphthene individually with phenanthraquinone and its mono and dinitro derivatives respectively,²⁻⁴ are compared, here too we get the order of depth of colour as

5-bromo dye > 4-bromo dye > 7-bromo dye > 6-bromo dye > parent dye.

Acenaphthyleneindigos (I a-d) :

Molar quantities of the reactants were dissolved in minimum volumes of hot glacial acetic acid, which were then mixed and refluxed for 20-30 minutes with the addition of conc. HCl (8 ml). The crude products were filtered, washed and crystallised from pyridine.

Phenanthreneindigos (III a-c) :

These dyes were similarly prepared from the constituents in glacial acetic acid solution and heating for 30 minutes with the addition of conc. HCl (10 ml). The crude dyes were filtered, washed and crystallised from pyridine.

Thioindogenides (II a-c) :

These dyes were obtained from equimolecular quantities of the reactants in boiling absolute ethanolic solution (20 ml), adding conc. HCl (2 ml) and heating under reflux for 15 minutes. The crude dyes were filtered, washed and crystallised from suitable solvents several times to get the pure products.

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